

Conventions and reference systems used by NDAC (Rev. 2)

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The following text supersedes the last paragraph of Section 5.1 *The starmapper geometry*.

The starmapper geometry is described in field coordinates by means of the functions

$$w = w_{fh}^*(z) + \Delta w_{gh}(z) \quad (12)$$

for all combinations of indices f , g , and h , where $\Delta w_{gh}(z)$ is the medium-scale irregularity derived from the grid calibration document (ESA-HIP-09894). For brevity, and since only one of the starmappers is active at any time, the index h shall be dropped in the following. The most general representation of the functions $w_{fg}^*(z)$ is:

$$w_{f1}^*(z) = (h_{10} + h_{11}z + h_{12}z^2)f + w_{10} + w_{11}z + w_{12}z^2 \quad (13a)$$

$$w_{f2}^*(z) = (h_{20} + h_{21}^+z + h_{22}^+z^2)f + w_{20} + w_{21}^+z + w_{22}^+z^2 + h_f \quad (13b)$$

$$= (h_{20} + h_{21}^-z + h_{22}^-z^2)f + w_{20} + w_{21}^-z + w_{22}^-z^2 - h_f \quad (13c)$$

with (13b) valid for the upper branch of the chevron ($z > 0$) and (13c) for the lower ($z < 0$). The two parameters h_{-1} and h_{+1} are by definition zero in the NDAC data processing. They are included here for completeness, since they may appear in other contexts such as Tycho astrometry. The remaining 16 parameters, together with a reference value of the basic angle, uniquely determine the NDAC starmapper geometry. They may be transferred from RGO in a standard format described in Section 5.3 of the Great-Circle Reduction Programs Interface Document (GCID-6; Petersen 14 Aug 1990).

The geometric calibration performed at RGO does not determine all 16 parameters. E.g., in the calibration of 22 Oct 1990, all quadratic terms (w_{12} , h_{12} , w_{22}^+ , w_{22}^- , h_{22}^+ and h_{22}^-) are assumed to be zero. None of them is expected to contribute more than about 2 mas at the extreme values of z .

On theoretical grounds one expects that $h_{21}^+ \simeq h_{21}^- \simeq 2h_{11}$. This may be used as a check of the calibration, or perhaps as a means of reducing the number of free parameters, if such a need should arise.